

Funded by
the European Union

EU-CIEMBLY
Creating an Inclusive European Citizens' Assembly

Deliverable 3.1

Dataset of Empirical Results

PROJECT INFORMATION

Project number	101132694
Project acronym	EU-CIEMBLY
Project name	EU-CIEMBLY: Creating an Inclusive European Citizens' Assembly
Project website	https://www.eu-ciembly.eu/en/home

DELIVERABLE INFORMATION

Title	Dataset of Empirical Results
Deliverable	3.1
Work Package	3
Leader	University of Essex
Authors	Anastasia Karatzia, Niall O'Connor, Samantha Woodward, Sarah Noles, Logan Sayles, Eric Jensen
Contributors	Rebecca Warren, Ileana Steccolini
Authors' acknowledgements	We thank all interviewees and dataset holders for their cooperation and contribution to the content of this deliverable.
Reviewers	Alexandra Aragão, Dulce Lopes, Giulia Sandri
Type	DATA
Due date	31 July 2025
Submission date	31 July 2025
Dissemination level	PUBLIC
License	CCBY

DOCUMENT HISTORY

Version	Date	Author	Comments
V0.1	30 June 2025	UE, IMI	First version
V0.2	15 July 2025	UE, IMI	Version after review
V0.3	23 July 2025	UE, IMI	Version after changes by authors
V1	29 July 2025	UE, IMI	Final version after post-review check and final changes by authors

How to cite this deliverable: Karatzia A., O'Connor N., Woodward W., Noles S., Sayles L., and Jensen E. (2025) *Dataset of Empirical Results*. EU-CIEMBLY Deliverable 3.1. <https://www.eu-ciembly.eu/en/home>

LIST OF ABBREVIATIONS

PMIMG	People belonging to multiple intersecting marginalised groups
WP	Work Package
RQ	Research question
SQ	Survey question

This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon Europe research and innovation program under grant agreement number 101132694. This deliverable reflects only the authors' views. The Commission is not responsible for its content or any use that may be made of the information it contains.

EXECUTIVE SUMMARY

Deliverable 3.1 consists of the datasets collected during the empirical research element of the EU-CIEMBLY project. These datasets include data collected (i) through qualitative interviews with individuals involved in the organisation, implementation, and evaluation of citizens' assemblies and (ii) through quantitative secondary data analysis of existing evaluation data from two past citizens' assemblies. The deliverable takes the form of (1) the present Explanatory Note and (2) the complete datasets which due to their size and complexity have been included in the [project's community page on Zenodo](#). The dataset includes (i) the anonymised transcripts of the interviews conducted by the project team, which provide insights into the perceptions of individuals directly involved in planning, conducting, and evaluating citizens' assemblies on the ground, as well as (ii) the secondary data analysis dataset, which offers insights into the perceptions of individuals who have participated in a citizens' assembly as participants. The interviews were led by the University of Essex team and the secondary data analysis was led by the Institute for Methods Innovation (IMI) team. This Note explains the methodology behind each of these activities, and illustrates how the activities build on previous tasks of the project, and how they will feed into subsequent work. Essentially, Deliverable 3.1 represents the conclusion of the data collection phase of the EU-CIEMBLY project's empirical research. The next phase of the project consists of analysing the collected data to advance the project's aims and objectives in designing (Work Package 3) and eventually piloting (Work Package 4) the model citizens' assemblies to be tested in practice.

TABLE OF CONTENTS

I. Introduction	7
II. The Background to the Project's Empirical Research	7
III. Methodological Notes	14
III.1. Methodological note on interviews	14
III.2. Methodological note on secondary data analysis	21
IV. Conclusion	33
V. Appendices	35
Appendix 1. Participant Information Sheet - Interview	36
Appendix 2. Consent Form - Interviews	40
Appendix 3. Interview Questions Guide	43
Appendix 4. Participant Information Sheet - Secondary Data Analysis	47
Appendix 5. Participant Consent Form - Secondary Data Analysis	50
References	52

EU-CIEMBLY Deliverable 3.1

Explanatory Note to the EU-CIEMBLY Dataset of Empirical Results

I. Introduction

Deliverable 3.1 marks the conclusion of the first 18 months of the EU-CIEMBLY project by presenting data collected by the project team for the empirical research element of the project. It consists of data that we collected through qualitative interviews with individuals involved in the organisation, implementation, and evaluation of citizens' assemblies; and, through quantitative secondary data analysis of existing evaluation data from two past citizens' assemblies. The combination of these two methods of data collection has allowed us to collect a rich set of data.

This Explanatory Note explains the design of the two elements of the empirical study, the methodology behind the datasets, and how we intend to use the data going forward.

The complete dataset is available on the [project's community page on Zenodo](#) and includes (i) **the anonymised transcripts of the interviews** conducted by our team, which provide insights into the perceptions of individuals directly involved in planning, conducting, and evaluating citizens' assemblies on the ground, as well as (ii) **the secondary data analysis dataset**, which offers insights into the perceptions of individuals who have participated in a citizens' assembly as participants. The secondary data analysis has additionally provided information on how persons belonging to different social groups have experienced citizens' assemblies differently. The interviews were led by the University of Essex team and the secondary data analysis was led by the IMI team.

II. The Background to the Project's Empirical Research

The work that supports this deliverable started in the fifth month of the EU-CIEMBLY project, and spans various stages of the project's life so far (Month 19). The **starting point** was the task of mapping existing citizens' assemblies at the local, national, and transnational levels (Task 3.1). This exercise, which took place three months after the

beginning of the project, had **an exploratory aim**. Instead of attempting a general mapping of existing citizens' assemblies at EU and Member State level, as initially indicated in the grant agreement, we decided to adopt an approach that was **more targeted** towards identifying elements of intersectionality in current citizens' assembly practice.¹ This approach allowed the project team to review existing forms of citizens' assemblies and gain familiarity with key design characteristics and how intersectionality considerations might - or might not - be reflected in those characteristics. The exercise involved eight project partner teams, who were given the deliberately broad task of exploring the design choices behind local, national, and transnational citizens' assemblies while looking to highlight aspects of particular relevance to the project. Such aspects were described as including, but not limited to: direct or indirect references to intersectionality considerations, specific features for encouraging the engagement of citizens belonging to different social groups / the intersection of social groups, or features to ensure diversity of participants.

Members from eight partners of the EU-CIEMBLY project team were allocated a selection of countries to explore, both from within and outside the EU, and were asked to exercise their judgement as to whether the mapping of a particular assembly might usefully contribute to the aims of the project. Adopting a pragmatic approach, the allocation of countries took place with consideration for the individual researcher's background and local knowledge, as well as linguistic abilities. In countries where a large number of similarly conducted assemblies have taken place (e.g. Ireland), the most recently held assembly was examined in depth, noting any innovations or differences in approach in comparison to previous assemblies.

The databases of [Politicize](#), [Burgerrat.de](#), [Participedia](#) and [OECD](#) were used as the basis for the search and review of citizens' assemblies, but team members were additionally encouraged to search more widely for examples of good practice within their allocated countries. The template below, inspired by the project's initial framework for citizens' assembly design, was completed by the team members:

¹ A number of other databases already provide a wealth of information on existing forms of citizens' assembly. Among others, see the databases of [Politicize](#), [Burgerrat.de](#), [Participedia](#) and [OECD](#) from which we benefited for the purpose of completing Task 3.1.

EU-CIEMBLY WORK PACKAGE 3	
TASK 3.1 MAPPING OF EXISTING CITIZENS' ASSEMBLIES	
CITIZENS' ASSEMBLY MAPPING TEMPLATE	
Characteristics of the Assembly	Name and Level of the Assembly:
When? (Topic and timing)	
How? (Institutional set-up and rules, including linguistic considerations)	
Who? (Participants, experts and facilitators recruitment)	
What? (Impact and influence on decision-making process)	
Additional Information (e.g. Who might we approach for the purpose of the interviews?)	
Notes	
Useful links	

Figure 1. EU-CIEMBLY Task 3.1 template for mapping existing citizens' assemblies

A total of **106** citizens' assemblies were included in the final mapping spreadsheet. It included examples from across **17 EU Member States, five non-EU countries, and from transnational practice**, including the EU's experience with citizens' panels during and after the Conference for the Future of Europe, as illustrated below in Figure 2. The below charts are intended to act as a visual aid rather than to suggest comparability between the number or type of citizens' assemblies analysed by country:

MAPPING CITIZENS' ASSEMBLIES IN PRACTICE

Exercise completed under Task 3.1

Figure 2: Results of the mapping conducted under EU-CIEMBL Y Task 3.1

The outcome of the above mapping exercise, considered alongside the research that was being simultaneously conducted under Work Package 2 of the project, informed the design of the empirical element of our study, i.e. of the interviews and the secondary data analysis:

Figure 3. Illustration of the relationship between the empirical elements of Work Packages 2 and 3

Further details on the methodology that was followed for each part of the empirical research supporting the datasets can be found in the respective **Methodological Notes** in the next section. These Notes aim to explain the design of the methodology and support the reader in engaging with the actual datasets (e.g. by explaining the anonymisation process for the interviews and the data transformation applied to the evaluation datasets). Additionally, the Methodological Note on Secondary Data Collection explains why the initial plan for the ‘survey’ element of the project (Task 3.3) was adapted from primary data collection of at least 50 people who have participated in previous citizens’ assemblies, to conducting a more ambitious secondary data analysis on **existing evaluation datasets** in order to produce a larger sample and improve our attempt to conduct an intersectional analysis.

The datasets collected from the interviews and the secondary data analysis aim to support two key parts of the project going forward. Firstly, the datasets are currently being analysed by the project team to feed into the evaluation stage of the project, where we study the extent to which intersectionality is being considered in the design, implementation, and evaluation of selected citizens’ assemblies in practice (Deliverable 3.3). This part of the project aims to complement the work that has already taken place under Work Package 2, which found that intersectionality does not feature prominently in the literature on, and the theory behind, citizens’ assemblies. Secondly, the datasets have been feeding into the project’s work on designing the model Citizens’ Assemblies that will be piloted in 2026 (Deliverable 3.4). For example, quotes from the interviews that relate to the theme of ‘facilitation’ have fed into our design of the facilitation strategies of the three pilots, while the methodological challenges faced by the team in collecting evaluation data from existing citizens’ assemblies has fed into our discussions on designing an evaluation strategy for our pilots. Figure 4 below represents the link between, on the one hand, Tasks 3.2 and 3.3 and, on the other hand, Deliverables 3.3 and 3.4:

Figure 4. The relationship between Tasks 3.2 and 3.3 and Deliverables 3.3 and 3.4

Future research

Beyond the confines of the EU-CIEMBLY project, we hope that the datasets from the interviews and the secondary data analysis will be of use to other stakeholders, such as researchers, civil society actors, and policy makers, who are interested in the topic of citizens' assemblies and particularly in intersectionality in citizens' assembly practice. To avoid unnecessary duplication, and for ease of access we have decided not to add the datasets directly to this Explanatory Note, but instead to make them directly available on [the project's community profile in Zenodo](#). As such, we have deposited both the anonymised interview transcripts and the secondary evaluation datasets to Zenodo, in line with the principle of **open access to research data** stipulated in the project's Data Management Plan.

Ethics

Both the interview and the secondary data analysis parts of the EU-CIEMBLY project's empirical research aspect (Work Package 3) were designed based on University of Essex guidelines for ethical approval of research involving participants. Our ethics application was reviewed by the project co-ordinator and the project's Societal, Ethics, and Gender Laboratory (SEGLAB). The project received **ethical approval** by the University of Essex (decisions number ETH2324-0311 and ETH2425-0609).

We are grateful to the interview participants and the dataset holders for their contribution to our project.

III. Methodological Notes

III.1. Methodological note on interviews

Here, we outline the methodology used to conduct qualitative interviews, which were aimed at understanding and qualitatively analysing the practical operation of citizens' assemblies, with a focus on exploring the extent to which intersectionality or intersectionality-related concepts have been incorporated into citizens' assemblies **in practice**. In what follows, we explain our ethics-driven approach to designing and conducting the interviews. The dataset of the anonymised interview transcripts can be found in [the project's community profile in Zenodo](#).

As mentioned above, the interviews for the project received ethical approval from the University of Essex (decision number ETH2324-0311) which was designed to cover all project partners involved in the interview data collection and/or analysis. The principle of informed consent has guided the design and delivery of the Participant Information Sheet (Appendix 1) and Consent Form (Appendix 2).

Recruitment of participants took place only after the granting of ethical approval. A total of 15 semi-structured interviews were conducted with individuals who were involved in the organisation of at least one citizens' assembly at the local, national, or transnational level. The majority of the interviewees fulfilled more than one role within the relevant citizens' assemblies and were involved with the organisation (deciding topics, location, managing logistics etc), facilitation (ensuring fair discussion and deliberation throughout the process), and/or evaluation (designing and carrying out surveys or interviews with participants on their experiences) of citizens' assemblies.

Developing the Interview Guide

The wider project team provided input and feedback into the design of a **semi-**

structured interview guide (Appendix 3). The interview guide was designed with a narrative approach in mind, using open-ended questions and aiming to get the participant to begin by explaining the background and their role in citizens’ assemblies, explore their experiences of working on citizens’ assemblies, and then reflect on those experiences. The main section of the interview focused on the participants’ experiences, and the Interview Guide was divided using the categories of citizens’ assembly design characteristics outlined in Deliverable 2.2 of the project which were (1) Governance and Organisation (When and How), (2) Selection and Recruitment (Who), and (3) Facilitation and Deliberation (What). This is demonstrated in the figure below from Deliverable 2.2 that shows the initial project framework for citizens’ assembly design.

Framework for a Citizens’ Assembly Design				
Intersectionality (infuses the design of the Citizens’ Assembly in achieving the intended qualities)	Design Choices			
	When?	How?	Who?	What?
	(topic and timing)	(institutional set-up and rules)	(participants, experts and facilitators)	(impact and influence on decision-making processes)
	Qualities (characterising each element of the Citizens’ Assembly)			
	Equality			
	Inclusion			
(High Quality) Deliberation				

Figure 5. The EU-CIEMBLY project’s initial framework for citizens’ assembly design

Through mapping existing citizens’ assemblies under Task 3.1 as described in the Introduction of this Explanatory Note, we had found that ‘intersectionality’ did not explicitly feature in most of the reports that examined or evaluated existing citizens’

assemblies. In instances where intersectionality was mentioned, this was a limited reference rather than playing a key role in the design or execution of a citizens' assembly. An example is the Chairman's Report on the Irish Citizens' Assembly on Gender Equality (An Tionól Saoránach, 2021, p. 89). As such, and to avoid **prejudicing** the discussion with a **preconceived concept of intersectionality**, we decided not to ask directly about intersectionality in interviews. Instead, we designed the Interview Guide to include questions focused on **inclusion, equality, and diversity** as values informing the design of citizen's assemblies, and to allow themes of intersectionality to emerge organically through the interviewer's prompts during the interview. Overall, this approach meant that the interview was led by the participant's experience, understanding and language (Staller, 2022). However, as intersectionality was included in the Participant Information Sheet and in the overview given by the interviewer, some participants did reflect directly on intersectionality.

Identifying and recruiting interviewees

To identify potential interviewees, we started from the mapping of existing citizens' assemblies that was completed under Task 3.1. Project team members explored citizens' assemblies in countries from within and outside the EU, as well as examples of transnational citizens' assemblies, which showed design characteristics of interest to the project. The list of citizens' assemblies from that exercise was narrowed down by examining material (e.g. online information) and reports from citizens' assemblies included in the mapping exercise to identify a shortlist of assemblies based on scale (local, national, and transnational) and their relation to intersectionality such as scope, topic, recruitment and facilitation methods, use of language, and whether the assembly had taken place within the previous 24 months to maximise the potential for interviewing relevant individuals.

Key individuals involved in the citizens' assembly process were then identified through publicly available information and were approached via email from the University of Essex project team. In total, we contacted 35 individuals or organisations with an invitation, which resulted in 12 interviews. An additional 'snowball' technique was used to obtain further recommendations from participants about individuals or organisations to speak to following a successful interview which resulted in a further 3 interviews. While we initially contacted individuals or organisations for interviews based on the

shortlist criteria previously detailed, there remained some self-selection bias as participants' ability to participate depended on availability and interest in contributing to the project or its findings. We aimed to mitigate this by arranging interviews at the convenience of the participant and through the range of potential participants to ensure a diversity of views was captured (as demonstrated in Figure 6 below, which shows location and scale of citizens' assemblies covered in the interviews). Overall, the interviewees reflected on a range of assemblies of varying sizes from the local to the national and the transnational level and, most importantly, they reflected on their own experiences and insights regarding the organisation and implementation of citizens' assemblies in practice.

Interviews

15 semi-structured interviews were conducted in English, each lasting between 60 and 90 minutes. Before the recording began, time was allocated for the interviewer to give a brief and to discuss any questions or concerns. The discussions were led by the interviewee and aimed to build rapport between the interviewer and interviewee (Yow, 2016). As previously stated, 'intersectionality' was intentionally not directly included in the Interview Guide, but if the participants asked about the concept and the approach the project was taking, a brief overview was provided by the interviewer, drawn by the definitions provided from the work produced under Work Package 2. The interviews were conducted by team members from the University of Essex and IMI, who communicated with each other both before, throughout, and after the conclusion of the interviews in order to ensure data quality and robustness through consistency in their approach.

Ahead of each interview, the interviewer conducted some preliminary research to direct the interview and to narrow down the extensive Interview Guide. Within the interview, interviewer discretion was used to ask open questions related to the categories of interest, and follow-ups were dependent on the responses from participants, in line with a semi-structured approach (Wengraf, 2001). All the interviews were conducted using Zoom and the application's automatic audio transcription was used to create the initial transcripts of the interviews.

Preparation of the dataset

Following the interview, each automated audio transcript was then checked by the interviewer to ensure accuracy. A member of the project team then reviewed and anonymised each transcript. This editing process followed a very **light-touch approach**: minimal edits were done, to preserve the **verbatim transcript**. This was done to capture the full context of the interview and to allow re-usability of data by other researchers, who may wish to use the data for another purpose, such as speech analysis. This approach follows best practice in qualitative interviewing (Wengraf, 2001; Tilley, 2003; Thompson, 2017) to highlight the importance of hesitations, repetition, and the **preservation of the interviewee's voice in the transcript**.

Participants were offered the option of having transcripts anonymised or being named in future deliverables, publications or presentations. It was decided the **default position** would be to **anonymise** all transcripts unless otherwise requested by the participant. As many of the participants continue to work in the field of participatory democracy, this was to ensure that participants felt comfortable to speak candidly with the interviewer (Lancaster, 2016). Both interviewees and organisations were pseudonymised to ensure identifying information was not included as part of the transcript. However, three interviewees requested to be named in future works and as such these interviews include identifying details about the organiser and the citizens' assembly they were involved with (Interviews 8, 14 & 15).

For the purposes of consistency within our dataset, all interviewees and citizens' assemblies are pseudonymised (i.e. identifiable information has been removed and replaced with a new reference). Interviews are pseudonymised by number (1-15) and each of the citizens' assemblies described in the interviews has been pseudonymised with a corresponding Greek letter, as shown in Figure 6 below. Additional relevant contextual information has been provided for each assembly, while remaining broad enough to ensure the information shared does not make individual assemblies identifiable. Many of the interviewees were involved in multiple assemblies and some interviewees were involved in the same citizens' assembly as shown in Figure 6.

Participants were reassured throughout the process that they could withdraw at any time and determine how their data and information will be used. Participants were also given the option to review their transcripts and make any amendments to ensure accuracy. Edits to the transcript are denoted using square brackets, with '[...]' used to

show where any text has been removed either to remove identifiable information or at the request of the participant.

PSEUDONYMISATION OF INTERVIEWS				
Citizens' Assembly	Interview	Key features for analysis		
		Location (EU/non-EU)	Scale	Number of participants
Alpha	2	Non-EU	Local	1-50
Beta	2	Non-EU	Local	1-50
Gamma	2	Non-EU	Local	1-50
Delta	3	EU	Local	1-50
Epsilon	3	EU	Local	1-50
Zeta	4	EU	Transnational	150-200
Eta	5	EU	National	150-200
Theta	5	EU	Local	1-50
Iota	6	EU	Local	1-50
Iota	7	EU	Local	1-50
Zeta	7	EU	Transnational	151-200
Kappa	7	EU	Transnational	151-200
Lambda	8	EU	Local	1-50
Mu	9	EU	National	101-150
Nu	10	EU	Local	51-100
Nu	11	EU	Local	51-100
Xi	12	Non-EU	Local	1-50
Omicron	13	Non-EU	National	1-50
Pi	13	Non-EU	National	101-150
Rho	13	Non-EU	Local	1-50
Sigma	13	Non-EU	Local	1-50
Tau	13	Non-EU	Local	1-50
Upsilon	13	Non-EU	National	1-50
Phi	14	Non-EU	Local	1-50
Chi	14	Non-EU	Local	1-50
Psi	14	Non-EU	Local	1-50
Omega	15	Non-EU	National	200+

Sampi	1	Non-EU	Local	1-50
--------------	---	--------	-------	------

Figure 6. Pseudonymisation of interviews

Similarly, to ensure the highest possible level of anonymity while still maintaining the usefulness of the data for our research, each of the organisations referenced have been pseudonymised with a corresponding letter of the Latin alphabet (Figure 7). The role of different organisations was highlighted by interviewees in a range of contexts for example, as commissioning bodies, employers, collaborators or service providers for the citizens' assembly including support with recruitment, facilitation or evaluation. Additional context for organisations has been added in the form of a 'descriptor' to describe the nature of the organisation while ensuring that identifying data remains confidential. As such, organisations have been sorted into categories depending on the nature of the organisations. Some of the interviewees referred to multiple organisations within the interview as shown by Figure 7:

PSEUDONYMISATION OF ORGANISATIONS		
Interview	Organisation	Descriptor
1	B	Nonprofit
2	A	Public
3	C	Private
3	D	Agency
3	E	Public authority
3	F	Private
4	G	Commissioning body
4	H	Public authority
5	I	Private
6	J	Public
6	K	Research institution
6	L	Public authority
7	K	Private
7	L	Public authority
7	G	Commissioning body
7	M	Private
7	J	Public
9	N	Private
9	O	Private
9	P	Research institute
9	Q	Public
10	R	Advocacy
10	S	Public authority
10	T	Nonprofit
12	U	Social enterprise
12	V	Nonprofit
13	W	Nonprofit
13	X	Public
14	T	Nonprofit

Figure

7.

Pseudonymisation of organisations

III.2. Methodological note on secondary data analysis

Here, we outline the methodology used to conduct secondary analysis of evaluation data from existing citizens' assemblies. As mentioned in the Introduction to this Explanatory Note, our approach towards this quantitative, 'survey' element of the empirical study of the project changed as the project progressed. According to the

description of Task 3.3 in the EU-CIEMBLY Description of Action, our initial plan for this part of the empirical study was to survey 50 participants who have participated in citizens' assemblies and who could provide insights into their perception of those assemblies. As the project evolved, we decided to take a more targeted approach: instead of surveying a very small sample of 50 participants on their overall perceptions, we decided to try an 'intersectional analysis' - in other words, to explore patterns and trends in how people belonging to multiple intersecting marginalised groups experienced different elements of the citizens' assembly. In methodological terms, this required the collection of a full range of demographic data about each participant in addition to data about their experience, in order to be able to isolate groups with particular intersecting demographic characteristics (e.g. Black queer women in their 60s with disabilities) and examine how their responses might differ from persons with other sets of characteristics. In theory, this would be best achieved by gathering an extremely large dataset, to ensure the number of people populating each intersectional demographic group is high enough to draw out meaningful and generalisable findings. As such, we decided to alter our less statistically ambitious approach from primary data collection of at least 50 people who have participated in previous citizens' assemblies, to conducting secondary data analysis on multiple evaluation datasets in order to produce a larger sample and improve our ability to conduct an intersectional analysis.

The design of this part of the empirical study was informed by the combination of the work done both under Work Package 2 and in the mapping of citizens' assembly practice. Based on this, the team designed the following research questions that guided the secondary data collection:

Research questions that guided the secondary data collection:

How are the experiences of PMIMG (people belonging to multiple, intersecting, marginalised groups) different to those of participants belonging to other social groups?

This includes the following sub-questions:

1. How were different elements (such as facilitation, deliberation, governance, etc.) of Citizens' Assemblies (CAs) perceived by participants from different social groups?

2. How inclusive were CAs, in terms of representation, process, outputs and outcomes, from the perspectives of participants belonging to different social groups?

- A. Representation (diversity as an indication of inclusivity): Includes comments and perceptions about the socio-demographic make-up of the Assembly; if certain types of people dominated conversations; if participants felt like there was a diverse range of experts; if participants felt like there was a diverse range of facilitators.
- B. Process: Inclusive in terms of (i) design/organisation (ii) recruitment / selection, (iii) facilitation and deliberation, (iv) effectiveness of mechanisms for accommodating different language needs from the perspective of participants.
- C. Outputs: Do PMIMG participants feel their perspectives are included in citizens' assembly outputs? Do these participants feel a sense of co-ownership of citizens' assembly outputs?
- D. Outcomes: Do PMIMG feel a personal impact (e.g. a change in attitude or view on a topic, confidence, or sense of political agency), as a result of participation in the citizens' assembly?

3. What was the impact of technology on participants' perception of the CA? Were there differences in experiences based on online versus face-to-face formats? Was the use of technology experienced differently depending on social groups?

4. What are the drivers of non-participation in citizens' assembly by potential participants from different social groups? (by non-participation we mean citizens declining to participate in the citizens' assembly at all, and citizens not engaging while in the citizens' assembly, and citizens dropping out of the citizens' assembly).

Sampling and data management

To address the research questions, a wide sample of 33 citizens' assemblies across Europe conducted within the last 5-10 years were scoped for suitability. Factors assessed included: sample size, extent and relevance of member experience data collected, extent of demographic data collected, evaluation quality (e.g., if pre- and post- measures were utilised to measure participant outcomes rather than only post), availability of a publicly downloadable dataset, and accessibility of organiser contact details. Of the 33 citizens' assemblies scoped, 29 met the minimum range of

demographic variables identified as relevant by the project team to move on to scoping member experience variables. These variables included gender, age, ethnicity, nationality, education level, physical ability, work status, home ownership, and the possibility of objective household income and inferred social class. Of these 29 citizens' assemblies that met the minimum range of demographic variables, 14 citizens' assemblies contained participant experience surveys with questions and timeframes suitable to the purposes of this research. However, comprehensive access to the attached demographic data of the participants necessary for cross tabulation required direct requests to dataset holders which was frequently difficult to achieve.

Of these 14 citizens' assemblies, we were able to successfully collect anonymised evaluation survey datasets from organisational data holders across three countries: Scotland, Spain, and Denmark. However, the datasets from We Do Democracy-run citizens' assemblies in Denmark did not link any demographic data to individual assembly members' responses about their experience, meaning this dataset was not ultimately included in our analysis. This meant that our secondary analysis ultimately focused on two datasets, namely those related to the Citizens' Assembly for the Climate of Catalonia, and the Scotland Climate Assembly.

As a result of this work, two anonymised evaluation survey datasets were collected from organisational data holders across two distinct locations: Scotland (part of the UK) and Catalonia (part of Spain). Organisational representatives for both were provided with a Participant Information sheet and were asked to return a signed Consent Form. These can be found in Appendix 4 and 5, respectively.

The datasets were standardised and prepared to ensure compatibility for statistical analysis. Full details on variables and cases in each dataset and the associated codebooks are provided in the [Zenodo](#) submission.

Quantitative analysis approaches

To conduct secondary analysis of evaluation data from existing citizens' assemblies, we employed two main methods of quantitative analysis. Both methods employed descriptive statistics because of the relatively modest sample size, particularly when identifying patterns at a detailed intersectional level (e.g., combining age and gender at the independent variable level). The sample size available (particularly at this

detailed level) would be insufficient for multivariate inferential statistics. As previously indicated, the purpose of these analyses is identifying trends in PMIMG experiences of citizens' assemblies to inform the next deliverables of the project. The full descriptive statistical detail developed for this work is available in the open datasets published on Zenodo.

Aggregate analysis. First, an aggregate analysis combined data from evaluation datasets for Scotland's Climate Assembly and the Citizens' Assembly for the Climate of Catalonia. This approach allowed for three-way crosstabulations to be generated, providing cross-contextual insights into different demographic experiences of citizens' assemblies. A three-way crosstabulation is a method used to examine the relationship between three categorical variables simultaneously. We have used three-way crosstabulations to explore how citizens' assembly experience varied not only by gender but also across different age groups. This approach enabled us to identify whether patterns in experiences in the assemblies differed within specific gender–age combinations. For example, instead of comparing experiences by gender alone, we could observe whether men, women and those identifying in another way within the same age group (e.g., 29 and under, 30-44, 45-64, 65+) reported similar or different ratings of their experiences. Conversely, we could also examine whether experience varied by age group within each gender category. This layered analysis provides greater insight into how perceptions differed across demographic intersections, helping to avoid overly general conclusions that might overlook important subgroup variation.

In order to implement this approach, both datasets were cross-referenced to identify where the same demographic and member experience variables were asked, so the data could be merged. Demographic data relating to gender and age were collected for both evaluations. In terms of member experience variables, 11 topic areas were identified for which similar survey questions were utilised across both evaluations. In order to merge the data from both evaluations to conduct aggregate analysis, some data transformation was required. Table 1 below shows the recoding that was implemented, grouping the variables from both evaluations by the core concept they measure.

Table 1: Comparable variables and recoding approach across Scotland’s Climate Assembly and Citizen’s Assembly for Climate of Catalonia evaluation datasets

Core concept	Scotland wording (item code)	Catalonia wording (item code)	Scotland original response options	Catalonia original response options	New dichotomised categories
Gender	Gender (GEN)	Gender (GEN)	Man	Male	Man
			Woman	Female	Woman
			In another way		In another way
Age	Age group (AGE)	Age (AGE)	19-24, 25-29	16-24, 25-29	29 and under
			30-44	30-44	30-44
			45-64	45-64	45-64
			65-74, 75+	65-74, 75+	65+
Diversity and representation	“The Assembly is diverse enough to ensure a broad range of perspectives are considered” (ASB_DIV_MED)	“Do you think the people in the Assembly reflect the social diversity of Catalonia?” (ASB_SOC_DIV)	Strongly disagree Tend to disagree	Not at all, Little	Negative
			I don't know, Neither agree nor disagree		Exclude
			Tend to agree Strongly agree	Quite a bit, A lot	Positive

Equal chance to speak	“I have had ample opportunity in the small-group discussions to express my views” (GRP_DISC_MED)	“During the debate, do you think everyone had the opportunity to speak and participate?” (DEB_OPP)	Tend to agree Strongly agree	Not at all, Little	Negative
			I don't know, Neither agree nor disagree		Exclude
			Strongly disagree Tend to disagree	Quite a bit, A lot	Positive
Feeling that contributions were listened to	How much do you agree or disagree with the following statements about the Assembly as a whole, and about your experience as a whole?: I feel that my contributions have been listened to by the other Assembly members (CONTR_LIST)	Are you satisfied with your level of participation during the debate/work sessions? (PART_SAT)	Tend to agree Strongly agree	Not at all, Little	Negative
			I don't know, Neither agree nor disagree		Exclude
			Strongly disagree Tend to disagree	Quite a bit, A lot	Positive
Facilitator neutrality	“The break-out-room facilitator sometimes tried to influence the group with their own ideas” (FAC_INFL_MED)	“Do you think the facilitation team remained neutral?” (FAC_TEAM_NEUT)	Tend to agree Strongly agree	Not at all, Little	Negative
			I don't know, Neither agree nor disagree		Exclude
			Strongly disagree Tend to disagree	Quite a bit, A lot	Positive

Facilitator encouragement of debate	"The break-out room facilitator made sure that opposing arguments were considered" (FAC_ARG_MED)	"Did the facilitation team help and encourage the debate?";	Tend to agree Strongly agree	Not at all, Little	Negative
			I don't know, Neither agree nor disagree		Exclude
			Strongly disagree Tend to disagree	Quite a bit, A lot	Positive
Information fairness & balance	"The information I have received during the Assembly weekend has been fair and balanced between different viewpoints" (ASB_FAIR)	"Do you think there are relevant perspectives ... that were not covered in the training sessions?" (TRN_PER_MIS)	Strongly disagree Tend to disagree	Quite a bit, A lot	Negative
			I don't know, Neither agree nor disagree		Exclude
			Tend to agree Strongly agree	Not at all, Little	Positive
Contribution reflected in recommendations	How much do you agree or disagree with the following statements about the Assembly as a whole, and about your experience as a whole?: My views are reflected in the finalised goals and recommendations (GRP_GOREC_T7)	"Do you think your opinions have been included in the final recommendations?" (OPN_INC)	Tend to agree Strongly agree	Not at all, Little	Negative
			I don't know, Neither agree nor disagree		Exclude
			Strongly disagree Tend to disagree	Quite a bit, A lot	Positive

Clarity of purpose/process	“The purpose of the weekend was well explained” (WK_PURP_MED)	“Were the objectives of the debate sessions clear?” (DEB_OBJ_CLR)	Tend to agree Strongly agree	Not at all, Little	Negative
			I don't know, Neither agree nor disagree		Exclude
			Strongly disagree Tend to disagree	Quite a bit, A lot	Positive
Confidence in uptake of recommendations	“I am confident that the Assembly report will be taken seriously by Parliament and political parties” (REP_SER)	“Do you think the Assembly’s recommendations will be adopted by the Government of Catalonia?” (REC_GOV_ADOPT)	Tend to agree Strongly agree	Not at all, Little	Negative
			I don't know, Neither agree nor disagree		Exclude
			Strongly disagree Tend to disagree	Quite a bit, A lot	Positive
Interest in future participation	“To what extent do you agree or disagree with the following statements: Taking part in this citizens' assembly has made me want to be more involved in other aspects of Government decision making” (GOV_INVOL_T8)	Would you be willing to participate in another citizens' Assembly? (PART_NEXT_ASB)	Tend to agree Strongly agree	Not at all, Little	Negative
			I don't know, Neither agree nor disagree		Exclude
			Strongly disagree Tend to disagree	Quite a bit, A lot	Positive

Assessments of speaker quality	How helpful did you find the following activities for your learning about climate change and how to tackle it across the Assembly as a whole?: Presentations by speakers (SPK_PRES)	Did the speakers and trainers explain the discussed topics well? (SPK_TRN_EXP)	Tend to agree Strongly agree	Not at all, Little	Negative
			I don't know, Neither agree nor disagree		Exclude
			Strongly disagree Tend to disagree	Quite a bit, A lot	Positive

Bivariate analysis. Second, bivariate analysis is applied separately for each citizens' assembly dataset using two-way crosstabulations. This involves examining the relationship between one demographic variable (e.g. gender, age, or ethnicity) and one member experience variable (e.g. their rating of how inclusive they perceived the facilitation process to be). These two-way crosstabulations allowed for the identification of patterns and differences across the full range of demographic characteristics each dataset captured (gender, age, and ethnicity for Scotland's Climate Assembly; gender, age, place of birth, education level, and language for the Citizens' Assembly for the Climate of Catalonia) to explore differences in experiences and perceptions among various social groups participating in the assemblies. Unlike three-way crosstabulations (which incorporate a third variable to reveal more complex subgroup patterns), two-way tables provide a more straightforward view of relationships between two variables at a time.

Criteria for selecting member experience variables on which to run analyses

The primary aim guiding the selection of member experience variables on which to conduct analyses in each dataset was to ensure a spread of valid insights that respond to the research questions, and sub-questions within them (10 in total) for this task. To ensure this, a set of criteria for variables to be included was established:

- Variable has relevance to any of the 10 themes in the research questions;
- Variable draws out insights at the level of the assembly as a whole, rather than a specific session or day;
- Variable overlaps in meaning with another variable in a different dataset, opening up potential for aggregate analysis.

Variables in each citizens' assembly evaluation dataset were then screened and coded based on these criteria.

Limitations

While our final result over-delivers on our original task description by gathering data on a maximum of 153 participants (tripling our baseline requirement of 50 survey respondents), and by analysing demographic differences across gender, age,

ethnicity, place of birth, language, and education level, we encountered challenges which represent important methodological findings. These findings are important both for understanding the limitations of the data **in the context of our project**, and for exploring the possibility and prospects of **future efforts** in intersectional analysis of member experiences in citizens' assemblies.

In terms of the limitations to the conclusions we can draw from the data for our project, of primary concern here is the small sample sizes in several demographic groups. For example, in Scotland's Climate Assembly, only two participants identified their gender 'in another way', and there were only four non-White participants. Similarly, in the Citizens' Assembly for the Climate of Catalonia, there was only one participant with 'No formal education', only three with just 'Primary education', and fewer than ten participants in the 'Rest of Spain', 'South America' and 'Other' birthplace categories. While observed differences relating to these categories warrant attention, the strength, validity and reliability of conclusions on the basis of this data is limited. This is both a methodological issue and a reflection of how traditional sortition approaches to citizens' assembly sampling and recruitment can lead to involvement of very small numbers of PMIMG.

Regarding the limitations that have transpired and which concern the possibility and prospects of future efforts in intersectional analysis of member experiences in citizens' assemblies, three observations are relevant here:

Firstly, our understanding from our dataset scoping efforts is that it does not seem to be essential standard practice to link demographic data to participant responses in citizens' assemblies evaluations. This precludes basic analysis based on demographic characteristics, let alone a more complex intersectional analysis.

Secondly, even where demographic data were collected, there was unfortunately little consistency in the types, number, and response options within the demographic variables included in evaluations, limiting the possible scope of our intersectional analysis. For example, while both the datasets used a diverse set of demographic criteria to recruit participants (e.g., disability status, socio-economic background) these characteristics were not reported in either evaluations at the level of individual responses. This prevented us from being able to maximise the value of the data that had originally been collected in the secondary analysis.

Thirdly, due to the fact that the citizens' assemblies we were able to evaluate used a sortition approach to their sampling and recruitment, the numbers of people with particular minoritised identities (e.g. ethnic minorities, people of non-conforming gender identities, people with less formal education) were very small, limiting the strength and generalisability of our findings about these groups. Given that sortition is the default standard for citizens' assemblies, this limitation would likely be applicable to any effort to analyse intersectional patterns.

Having said that, overall the secondary data analysis approach has been, in our view, more productive (and based on a larger and more diverse sample base) than our initial plan to survey 50 individuals from past citizens' assemblies. In addition to allowing insights into the experiences of a larger number of participants from more than one assembly in distinct locales, it has revealed both demographic patterns in citizens' assemblies members' experiences, and broader methodological findings about citizens' assembly practice and research.

IV. Conclusion

Deliverable 3.1 marks the conclusion of the collection phase of EU-CIEMBLY's empirical research aspect. The next steps consist of analysing the collected data to advance the project's aims and objectives. Specifically, the findings from the interviews and the secondary data analysis will feed into the evaluation part of the project, as well as the design of the pilots that will take place in 2026. Beyond the findings about the experiences and insights of those involved in citizens' assemblies - either as organisers and facilitators, or as participants - the data collection phase has also indicated limitations about the extent to which an intersectionality-oriented method of analysis can be embedded into existing citizens' assemblies. Of those challenges, two are particularly interesting and merit further analysis: first, the quantitative element of the research has shown limitations in how citizens' assemblies currently collect socio-demographic data and has illustrated the effect of sortition, as the default standard for citizens' assemblies, on any effort to analyse intersectional patterns. Second, current practices do not explicitly engage with the concept of intersectionality. This raises the question of whether in conducting qualitative research on intersectionality in citizens' assemblies, it is necessary to be explicit about the meaning and potential value of intersectionality in their design and delivery. As

explained above, we adopted a more indirect approach in our qualitative interviews in order to probe interviewees' own understanding and experiences of intersectionality, but in future research it would be interesting to consider if a more explicit approach might yield different findings.

V. Appendices

Appendix 1. Participant Information Sheet - Interview

Participant Information Sheet

Interview for the research project EU-CIEMBLY: Creating an Inclusive European Citizens' Assembly

Dear participant,

The EU-CIEMBLY project team is carrying out research to address the need to introduce new forms of citizens' participation and deliberation in European Union (EU) political life and, particularly, an EU Citizens' Assembly whose design and implementation fully addresses issues of intersectionality, inclusiveness, and equality.

This project will provide the analytical framework and a prototype through which such a tool can be created in the form of a Citizens' Assembly that can be established at the EU level and with features allowing for the transfer of a modified prototype to the national and local levels of EU Member States.

As part of the project, we are seeking to understand the experiences of individuals involved in the organisation, administration, facilitation, and evaluation of existing citizens' assemblies. These experiences will help to shape the design of our prototype citizens' assembly model by helping us to identify which characteristics allow for the maximum level of inclusion, therefore addressing issues of intersectional discrimination and the effects of power relations on marginalised groups.

For further information on the project please visit: www.eu-ciembly.eu

What is the purpose of the study?

This study aims to interview experts, officials, and administrators responsible for the design, delivery, and evaluation of European Union and national participatory mechanisms, such as citizens' assemblies or citizen's panels.

The aim of the interviews is to explore the experiences of individuals involved in citizens' assemblies and to understand how variables related to the legal, administrative, and linguistic context of those assemblies influence citizen engagement and inclusion.

Why have I been invited to participate?

You have been invited to participate in this study because of your involvement in the organisation, administration, and/or facilitation of citizens' assemblies. Your participation will

provide valuable insight into the process and experience of designing and running citizens' assemblies.

Do I have to take part?

It is up to you to decide whether or not you wish to take part in this research study. If you do decide to take part, you will be asked to provide us your written consent. You are free to withdraw at any time, without giving a reason, until outputs have been generated (e.g. project reports and policy / academic publications etc). If you wish to withdraw from the study at any time, please contact the researchers, whose details can be found below.

What will happen to me if I take part?

If you decide to take part in this project, you will be asked to complete a consent form and have the opportunity to ask questions of the project team. You will then be invited to take part in an interview on Zoom, which will last around 60 minutes. Your interview will be conducted by a member of the project team, and you will have the opportunity to ask them any further questions you may have at the start of the interview. During the interview, you will be asked questions that relate to your experience with citizens' assemblies, the organisation and facilitation, as well as your reflections on what could be improved to promote diversity and inclusiveness in the design of the relevant assembly.

What are the possible disadvantages and risks of taking part?

Taking part in an interview will take up some of your time, but we will ensure that the interview takes place at your convenience. There are no risks in taking part in this interview.

What are the possible benefits of taking part?

The likely benefits of being involved are being able to share your experience and reflections of being involved in the organisation, administration, facilitation, or evaluation of citizens' assemblies, which will help to shape the findings of the EU-CIEMBL Y research project and help our attempts towards establishing a model for inclusive citizens' assemblies grounded in intersectionality.

Will my information be kept confidential?

All information collected will be securely treated and saved by the project team on Box, a secure cloud storage platform licenced to the University of Essex. It is up to you whether you wish to remain anonymous. You can specify your preference on the consent form for this project. If you decide to remain anonymous, your identifiable data will only be shared with essential members of the project team, including the interviewer and members of the

University of Essex listed as contacts below. The transcript of your interview will then be anonymised and any identifiable information will be removed before sharing with the wider project team. A copy of the information which we record about you, but not the other participants, can be provided, free of charge, on request.

We intend to retain the research data generated for at least 10 years following the end of the project. In addition, if you agree in your consent form, your anonymised information will be deposited as part of the EU-CIEMBLY project to an open access research repository to be determined by the project co-ordinator.

What is the legal basis for using the data and who is the Data Controller?

The legal basis for processing the data collected from this project is informed consent. The Data Controller for this project is the University of Essex and the contact is the University Information Assurance Manager (dpo@essex.ac.uk).

What should I do if I want to take part?

If you would like to take part in this research, please email the University of Essex project team at eu-ciembly@essex.ac.uk

What will happen to the results of the research study?

The results of the research will be used to inform and shape the findings of the EU-CIEMBLY project through a range of outputs including but not limited to reports, research publications, presentations, and blogs. Your information will be anonymised, and you will not be identifiable in any of the outputs from the project unless you choose to make your interview identifiable via the consent form. All outputs from the EU-CIEMBLY project will be available to the public.

Who is funding the research?

This project is being funded by the European Union's Horizon Europe Research and Innovation programme under grant agreement number 101132694.

Who has reviewed the study?

The study has been reviewed and received approval by the Ethics Sub-Committee at the University of Essex.

Concerns and complaints

If you have any concerns about any aspect of the study or you have a complaint, in the first instance please contact the Principal Investigator on the project, Dr. Anastasia Karatzia at

a.karatzia@essex.ac.uk and the project's Data Management and Protection Officer Fernando Borges at fernando.borges@ij.uc.pt. If you are still concerned, you think your complaint has not been addressed to your satisfaction, or you feel that you cannot approach the above persons, please contact the departmental Director of Research in the department responsible for this project, Professor Geoff Gilbert at g.gilbert@essex.ac.uk. If you are still not satisfied, please contact the University of Essex Research Integrity Manager, Mantalena Sotiriadou at ms21994@essex.ac.uk. Please include the ERAMS reference ETH2324-0311.

Research Team Members

Dr Anastasia Karatzia, Senior Lecturer, Essex Law School, a.karatzia@essex.ac.uk

Dr Niall O'Connor, Senior Lecturer, Essex Law School, n.oconnor@essex.ac.uk

Professor Ileana Steccolini, Professor, Essex Business School,
ileana.steccolini@essex.ac.uk

Dr Rebecca Warren, Senior Lecturer, Essex Business School,
rebecca.warren@essex.ac.uk

Dr Samantha Woodward, Senior Research Officer, Essex Law School,
s.woodward@essex.ac.uk

Appendix 2. Consent Form - Interviews

Participant Consent Form

Interview for the research project **EU-CIEMBLY: Creating an Inclusive European Citizens' Assembly**

Dear participant,

On behalf of the EU-CIEMBLY project team, we would like to thank you for your willingness to share your experiences with designing, organising, evaluating, or implementing a Citizens' Assembly and for your invaluable contribution to our study. If you agree to participate in this research project, you will be interviewed by a researcher of our team via Zoom. Your responses will be recorded through video and audio recording. These recordings, together with the transcript of the interview, will be used for the sole purpose of research and will be stored in secure systems, guaranteeing the privacy of any data you share with us. The data will then be analysed by the project team for the purposes of the study.

Please see the attached Participant Information Sheet for details about the study and your rights as a participant.

Please return a digitally signed copy, or a scan or photograph of a signed copy, of the completed form via email to euciembly@essex.ac.uk

We remain at your disposal should you have any questions regarding this form.

Kind regards,

The EU-CIEMBLY project team

Statement of Consent	Please initial each box
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> I confirm that I have read and understood the information provided in the Participant Information Sheet for the above study. I have had an opportunity to consider the information, ask questions and have had any questions satisfactorily answered. 	
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> I understand that my participation is voluntary and that I am free to withdraw from the project at any time without giving any reason and without penalty. I understand that any data collected up to the point of my withdrawal will be permanently deleted. I understand that, once project reports, academic publications, or other outputs 	

<p>have been published or circulated as final documents, it will not be possible to delete references to my interview in those documents.</p>	
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> I agree for this interview to be audio and video recorded. 	
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> I understand that the identifiable data provided by me will be securely stored and accessible only to members of the research team directly involved in the project, and confidentiality will be maintained. 	
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> I understand and consent to the fact that my data will be anonymised before being used in subsequent reports and research. 	<p>OR I would prefer that my data is not anonymised in subsequent reports and research. In those reports I would like the following to be my named role:</p> <p>_____</p> <p>_____</p>
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> I understand that the data collected will be used as part of research and publications of the EU-CIEMBL Y project. This will include reports to the European Union, research publications and other outputs. 	
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> I understand that the data collected about me may be used to support other research in the future and may be shared, according to my wishes as indicated above, with other researchers. 	

<ul style="list-style-type: none"> I give permission for the data I provide to be deposited, according to my wishes as indicated above, in a data repository as part of the wider EU-CIEMBLY project so that they will be made available for future research and learning activities by other individuals. 	
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> I agree to participate in the above study. 	

Participant Name

Date

Participant Signature

Researcher Name

Date

Researcher Signature

Please return a digitally signed copy, or a scan or photograph of a signed copy, of the completed form via email to eu-ciembly@essex.ac.uk

Appendix 3. Interview Questions Guide

EU-CIEMBLY (Creating an Inclusive European Citizens' Assembly)

ERAMS reference:ETH2324-0311

Interview Guide

Please note that the questions in this Interview Guide are designed to be used as part of a semi-structured interview. As such, the Guide is structured into themes (in bold letters) and indicative questions organised under these themes. Throughout the interview, additional questions may be posed depending on the participant's answers.

Background

- What citizens' assembly/ies (CAs) have you been involved in? Can you explain the purpose/aim of the CA?
- How did you become involved in this work?
- What was your role?
- Could you tell me a bit about what the role involved?
- How do you see the role of the Citizens' Assemblies?

Experience of being involved in the CA

- What was your experience of being involved in the citizens' assembly?
- Depending on the role within the CA, follow-ups will be asked about particular stages of the CA – broadly speaking to get the interviewee's views on what worked well and what was challenging:
 - **Governance, organisation**
 - *Topic* – How did you decide/the team decide on the topic of the Citizens' Assembly?
 - *Logistics* – Could you briefly talk me through the logistics of the Citizens' Assembly?
 - Were there any logistical considerations that needed to be made to cater for different types of people attending the assembly?
 - *The selection of experts* – What was the process of selecting experts?
 - *Innovation* – In designing the process, would you say you have tried to do something particularly innovative in the CA/ CAs you've been involved in, as compared to traditional ways of holding CAs?
 - **Selection and recruitment**
 - *Size of the CA* – How did you decide on the number of participants?
 - *Sampling* – How did you make decisions around sampling?
 - *Recruitment* – How did you make decisions around recruitment?
 - *Recruitment* – What recruitment methods did you use?
 - To what extent did you think that the selection – meaning both the sampling and the recruitment of participants - was representative? Why?

- *Innovation* – If there were no limits in resourcing and capacity, what would you have changed about the selection and recruitment of citizens to the CA/CAs that you have been involved in (with regards to maximising diversity, inclusivity or intersectionality)?
 - Do you believe that the CA/CAs that you have been involved in have positively impacted on representation in democratic settings? In what way?
- **Facilitation and deliberation**
- *Ground rules* – what kind of ground rules were set for deliberation? What guidance was given to facilitators?
 - *Ensuring fair and equal discussions* – How did you ensure fair discussions? What opportunities were given to participants to have an equal say in the deliberation?
 - *Use of experts/education* – What materials did you share with participants to facilitate their engagement, and in what form (text, pictures, infographics, videos)? Why?
 - *Consensus building and voting* –
 - What was the endpoint of the deliberation? (was it consensus?)
 - What were participants asked to produce? (was it a recommendation / set of recommendations / something else?)
 - What method did you use to enable the group to reach its recommendation(s)? (voting or other methods?)
 - Are there other things that you think you could have shared with citizens to facilitate higher levels of engagement?
- **Language**
- *Background* – When the topic was selected, were the needs of the different relevant language communities taken into account?
 - *Background* – Was the CA conducted in multiple languages or a single language. If the CA was monolingual: how did you arrive at the decision to cater to a single linguistic community?
 - If the CA was multilingual: how did you choose the linguistic communities to cater to?
 - *Reach* – How did you ensure that participants from different language communities learned about the CA?
 - *Selection and recruitment* – Did you purposefully recruit participants, facilitators and experts that speak languages other than the dominant language(s)? And what provisions were in place to allow them to use these languages?
 - *Facilitation and deliberation* – What language services were in place (e.g., translation and interpreting) to ensure that speakers of different

languages, language varieties, dialects, sociolects and registers were satisfactorily included in the process?

- **Outcomes (post-CA)**
 - *Outcomes* – What were the outcomes from the CA? How were these actioned?
 - Did the participants in the CA know of these outcomes at the point of recruitment? If so, do you think this has made a difference in their willingness to participate / engage with the discussions?
 - *Follow-up* – Do the people who engaged in the CA know what happened with the outcome of their deliberations?
 - Have you had any follow up contact with those involved in the CA?

- **Feedback**
 - *Evaluation and flexibility* – How did you evaluate the experience of participants in the CA? Were there multiple evaluation points (e.g. pre- and post-surveys / observations / interviews at various points of the CA)?
 - What were some of the significant points of feedback? What have been some of the changes made following feedback?

Reflections

- *What worked well* – Overall, what worked well about the CA(s) you were involved with?
- *Space for improvement* – What did you think could be changed/improved?
- *Challenges* – Were there any challenges you/the team identified? If so, could you tell us a bit about these?
- *Impact* – Overall, what are your reflections on the impact of the citizens' assembly?
- *Getting the interviewee to think outside the box* – If you had unlimited resources what would you do differently about the CA(s) you were involved in? Specifically, what would you change about the CA(s) in terms of representativeness?
 - Is there anything else that you would do differently if you were to do the CA(s) again?

Appendix 4. Participant Information Sheet - Secondary Data Analysis

Information Sheet for Data Holders

Collection of contemporaneous evaluation data for the research project EU-CIEMBLY: Creating an Inclusive European Citizens' Assembly

The EU-CIEMBLY project team is carrying out research to address the need to introduce new forms of citizens' participation and deliberation in European Union (EU) political life and, particularly, an EU Citizens' Assembly whose design and implementation fully addresses issues of intersectionality, inclusiveness, and equality. The project aims to develop recommendations on how citizens' assemblies can be more inclusive from an intersectional point of view.

As part of the project, we are seeking to understand the experiences of individuals who have participated in citizens' assemblies. By analysing existing evaluative data, we aim to identify which characteristics of citizens' assemblies allow for the maximum level of inclusion, which will help us understand the effects of power relations on marginalised groups and address issues of intersectional discrimination.

For further information on the project, please visit: www.eu-ciembly.eu

Through our research, we have identified assemblies that have collected evaluative feedback from their participants. We believe that you may hold public or non-public data that includes such evaluations. We would, therefore, like to request from you access to that data.

What is the purpose of the study?

The study aims to investigate evaluative data of citizens' assemblies and explore any historical comparisons, trends, and statistical analyses within and across datasets. We aim to examine data from citizens' assemblies that selected participants across three or more demographic variables to understand participants' experiences across the intersections of different social groups.

Why have I been invited to participate?

You have been invited to participate because we think you have access to data from a citizens' assembly that has already taken place, and which relate to demographic variables and/or experiences of the participants of that assembly.

What would I be asked to do if I took part?

We ask you to read and sign a consent form that states you have the appropriate consent in place to share your dataset with the EU-CIEMBLY project team and understand how our project team will use the data. Please return the signed consent form to us together with the relevant dataset(s) in an accessible format (or a link to those datasets), to research@methodsinnovation.org and eu-ciembly@essex.ac.uk.

What are the possible disadvantages and risks of taking part in this study?

Confirming that you have the permission to share and reuse the data, as well as sharing the data with us will take up some of your time, but this can be done at your convenience. We would be thankful to receive your response by [insert date].

What are the possible benefits of taking part in this study?

By sharing relevant datasets with our project, you will contribute to shaping our findings, and you will help our attempts to establish a prototype for inclusive citizens' assemblies grounded in intersectionality. If you wish, we can acknowledge your contribution to our study.

Will my information be kept confidential?

All information collected will be securely treated by project partners. IMI will be responsible for analysing the information that you share with us. The datasets may also be shared with relevant EU-CIEMBLY project partners including European Citizens Action Service, University of the Witwatersrand Johannesburg, University of Waikato, Victoria University of Wellington, Universidade de Coimbra, Universidad Complutense de Madrid and Make.org.

Once the analysis of data has been completed, it will be made available by the University of Essex and IMI to the wider EU-CIEMBLY project team via a shared Google Drive, with access for all members of the project.

We intend to retain the research data for at least 10 years following the end of the project. In addition, the datasets created from the analysis of your data and others will be deposited as part of the EU-CIEMBLY project to an open access research repository to be determined by the project co-ordinator. Further deposits may be made to research repositories as needed depending on the requests of data holders.

What is the legal basis for using the data and who is the Data Controller?

The legal basis for processing the data collected from this project is informed consent. The Data Controller for this project is the University of Essex and the contact is the University Information Assurance Manager (dpo@essex.ac.uk).

What should I do if I want to take part?

You should email the research team at research@methodsinnovation.org, attaching the signed consent form and the datasets in an accessible format. Please cc euciembly@essex.ac.uk in your email.

What will happen to the results of the research study?

The results of the research will be used to inform and shape the findings of the EU-CIEMBLY project through a range of outputs including but not limited to deliverables, reports, research publications, presentations, and blogs. All outputs from the EU-CIEMBLY project will be available to the public.

Who is funding the research?

This project is being funded by the European Union's Horizon Europe Research and Innovation programme under grant agreement number 101132694.

Who has reviewed the study?

The study has been reviewed by and received approval from the Ethics Sub-Committee at the University of Essex.

Concerns and complaints

If you have any concerns about any aspect of the study or you have a complaint, in the first instance, please contact the Principal Investigator on the project, Dr. Anastasia Karatzia at a.karatzia@essex.ac.uk and the project's Data Management and Protection Officer Fernando Borges at fernando.borges@ij.uc.pt. If you are still concerned, you think your complaint has not been addressed to your satisfaction, or you feel that you cannot approach the above persons, please contact the departmental Director of Research in the department responsible for this project, Professor Christopher Willett at cwillett@essex.ac.uk. If you are still not satisfied, please contact the University of Essex Research Integrity Manager, Mantalena Sotiriadou at ms21994@essex.ac.uk. Please include the ERAMS reference ETH2324-0311.

Research Team Members

Dr Anastasia Karatzia, Senior Lecturer, Essex Law School, a.karatzia@essex.ac.uk

Dr Niall O'Connor, Senior Lecturer, Essex Law School, n.oconnor@essex.ac.uk

Professor Ileana Steccolini, Professor, Essex Business School,
ileana.steccolini@essex.ac.uk

Dr Rebecca Warren, Senior Lecturer, Essex Business School,
rebecca.warren@essex.ac.uk

Dr Samantha Woodward, Senior Research Officer, Essex Law School,
s.woodward@essex.ac.uk

Dr Eric Jensen, CEO and Research Director, Institute for Methods Innovation,
eric@methodsinnovation.org

Appendix 5. Participant Consent Form - Secondary Data Analysis

Data holder consent form

Collection of contemporaneous evaluation data for the research project EU-CIEMBLY: Creating an Inclusive European Citizens' Assembly

The EU-CIEMBLY project team is carrying out research to address the need to introduce new forms of citizens' participation and deliberation in European Union (EU) political life and, particularly, an EU Citizens' Assembly whose design and implementation fully addresses issues of intersectionality, inclusiveness, and equality. The project aims to develop recommendations on how citizens' assemblies can be more inclusive from an intersectional point of view. For further information on the project, please visit: www.eu-ciembly.eu

As part of the project, we are seeking to understand the experiences of individuals who have participated in citizens' assemblies. By analysing existing evaluative data, we aim to identify which characteristics of citizens' assemblies allow for the maximum level of inclusion, which will help us understand the effects of power relations on marginalised groups and address issues of intersectional discrimination.

Through our research, we have identified assemblies that have collected evaluative feedback from their participants, and believe that you may hold public or non-public data that includes such evaluations. We would, therefore, like to request from you access to that data.

Please see the attached Participant Information Sheet for details about the study and your rights as a participant.

Please return a digitally signed copy, or a scan or photograph of a signed copy, of the completed form via email to research@methodsinnovation.org and euciembly@essex.ac.uk.

Statement of Consent	Please initial each box
I confirm that I have read and understood the information provided in the Participant Information Sheet for the above study. I have had an opportunity to consider the information, ask questions and have had any questions satisfactorily answered.	
I confirm that I am the data holder and have the authority to share the requested data.	
I confirm that the appropriate consent from participants to share the requested data for academic research purposes is in place.	
I agree for the requested data to be used by the EU-CIEMBLY project team as set out in the Participant Information Sheet.	

<p>I understand that the data shared will be used as part of research and publications of the EU-CIEMBLY project. This will include project deliverables, reports to the European Union, research publications and other outputs.</p>	
<p>I give permission for the data and the analysis produced from the data I share to be deposited in a data repository as part of the wider EU-CIEMBLY project so that they will be made available for future research and learning activities by other individuals.</p>	

Data holder Name

Date

Data holder Signature

Researcher Name

Date

Researcher Signature

Please return a digitally signed copy, or a scan or photograph of a signed copy, of the completed form via email to research@methodsinnovation.org copying euciembly@essex.ac.uk

References

An Tionól Saoránach (2021). Report of the Citizens' Assembly on Gender Equality. <https://citizensassembly.ie/wp-content/uploads/2023/02/report-of-the-citizens-assembly-on-gender-equality.pdf>

Lancaster, K. (2016). Confidentiality, anonymity and power relations in elite interviewing: conducting qualitative policy research in a politicised domain. *International Journal of Social Research Methodology*, 20(1), 93-103. DOI: 10.1080/13645579.2015.1123555

Staller, K. (2022). Confusing questions in qualitative inquiry: Research, interview, and analysis. *Qualitative Social Work*, 21(2), 227-234. <https://doi.org/10.1177/14733250221080533>

Wengraf, T. (2001). *Qualitative research interview: semi-structured, biographical and narrative methods*. SAGE Publications.

Yow, V. (2016). Interviewing Techniques and Strategies in Perks R. and Thomson A. (Eds.), *The Oral History Reader* pp. 153-178. Routledge. DOI: 10.4324/9781315671833-13